

“MAGISTRLAR” CERTIFICATE OF AWARD

We hereby present this certificate to

Tajetdinov Salamat

JAMIYAT RIVOJLANISH NAZARIYALARINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANDI

